

ANTI-PATTERNS CATALOG IN C

ANTI-PATTERN GENERAL DATA				
ID	TITLE			
C_G2	Missing ";" at end of line			
EXAMPLE:				
<pre> 6 printf("insira um nÃºmero:\n") 7 scanf("%d", &n) 8 printf("%d\n", n) </pre>				
ERROR TYPE:	X	Syntax	Semantics	Style
CONTENT:	- General			
IN WHAT LANGUAGE WAS THE MISTAKE MADE?	X	C	Python	
PROBLEM:				
Missing the ";" (semicolon) at the end of lines that require it will cause a syntax error and the code will not execute before the error is corrected.				
CONNECTIONS TO OTHER ANTI-PATTERNS:				
EVENTS				
Note: In the code snippets presented below, only the anti-pattern question of this table was analyzed. If other errors exist, these errors have been handled in other anti-patterns.				
EVENT 1				
Student Id: 2558		Total of submissions for the exercise:		3
The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 1.1				
<p style="text-align: center;">Error</p> <pre> 6 printf("insira um nÃºmero:\n") 7 scanf("%d", &n) 8 printf("%d\n", n) </pre>			<p style="text-align: center;">Fixed Error</p> <pre> 6 printf("insira um nÃºmero:\n"); 7 scanf("%d", &n); 8 printf("%d\n", n); </pre>	
Occurred in submission: 1			Fixed on submission: 2	
Observation:			Observation:	
EVENT 2				
Student Id: 2719		Total of submissions of the exercise:		3
The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 1.1				
<p style="text-align: center;">Error</p> <pre> 5 int num </pre>			<p style="text-align: center;">Fixed Error</p> <pre> 5 int num; </pre>	

<p>Occurred in submission: 1 Observation:</p>	<p>Fixed on submission: 2 Observation:</p>
EVENT 3	
<p>Student Id: 4738</p>	<p>Total of submissions of the exercise: 3</p>
<p>The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 1.1</p>	
<p style="text-align: center;">Error</p> <pre>7 printf("Digite um numero inteiro: ")</pre> <p>Occurred in submission: 2 Observation:</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Fixed Error</p> <pre>7 printf("Digite um numero inteiro: ");</pre> <p>Fixed on submission: 3 Observation:</p>
EVENT 4	
<p>Student Id: 5242</p>	<p>Total of submissions of the exercise: 14</p>
<p>The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 7.2</p>	
<p style="text-align: center;">Error</p> <pre>11 12 x=h*x h=x</pre> <p>Occurred in submission: 9 Observation:</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Fixed Error</p> <pre>11 12 x=h*x; h=x;</pre> <p>Fixed on submission: 10 Observation:</p>
A SUGGESTED SOLUTION	
FOR PROFESSORS	
<p>Explanation using blackboard and projector – reinforce the concept using Kahoot</p>	
FOR STUDENTS	
<p>Solve exercises, add code errors, and ask classmate to find them</p>	

ANTI-PATTERN GENERAL DATA

ID	TITLE		
C_GL1	Library call missing		
EXAMPLE:			
<pre style="background-color: #f0f0f0; padding: 10px; border: 1px solid #ccc;"> 1 int main (){ 2 int a; 3 scanf("%d", a); 4 printf("%d", a); 5 }</pre>			
ERROR TYPE:			
X	Syntax	Semantics	Style
CONTENT:			
- Library			
IN WHAT LANGUAGE WAS THE MISTAKE MADE?			
X	C	Python	
PROBLEM:			
When a command is actually a function, such as "scanf", "printf", "malloc," and so on, and these functions were developed within libraries, calling these is indispensable for the program to recognize such commands/functions.			
CONNECTIONS TO OTHER ANTI-PATTERNS:			
EVENTS			
<p>Note: In the code snippets presented below, only the anti-pattern question of this table was analyzed. If other errors exist, these errors have been handled in other anti-patterns.</p>			
EVENT 1			
Student Id: 2670		Total of submissions of the exercise: 4	
The exercise that was being solved:			
Exercise 1.1			
Error <pre style="background-color: #f0f0f0; padding: 5px; border: 1px solid #ccc;"> 1 int main (){</pre>	Fixed Error <pre style="background-color: #f0f0f0; padding: 5px; border: 1px solid #ccc;"> 1 # include <stdio.h> 2 int main (){</pre>	Occurred in submission: 1 Observation: The code does not compile. Missing library call containing Input and Output functions.	Fixed on submission: 3 Observation:
EVENT 2			
Student Id: 3167		Total of submissions of the exercise: 8	
The exercise that was being solved:			
Exercise 1.1			
Error	Fixed Error		

```

1 #include int main () {
2     int b = a;
3     scanf("%d", b);

```

```

1 #include <stdio.h>
2 int main(void){
3     int b;
4     scanf("%d", b);

```

Occurred in submission: 1
Observation:

Fixed on submission: 6
Observation:

EVENT 3

Student Id: 2040 Total of submissions of the exercise: 8

The exercise that was being solved:
Exercise 2.1

Error

```

1 int main()
2 {
3     int a,b;
4     scanf("%d %d" a,b);

```

Fixed Error

```

1 #include <stdio.h>
2 int main()
3 {
4     int a,b;
5     scanf("%d %d" a,b);

```

Occurred in submission: 1
Observation:

Fixed on submission: 3
Observation:

EVENT 4

Student Id: 5226 Total of submissions of the exercise: 11

The exercise that was being solved:
Exercise 3.3

Error

```

1 int main(){
2     int n, cont;
3     cont =0;
4     printf("");

```

Fixed Error

Occurred in submission: 1
Observation:

Fixed on submission:
Observation: The error has not been fixed.

A SUGGESTED SOLUTION

FOR PROFESSORS

Explanation using blackboard and projector – reinforce the concept using Kahoot

FOR STUDENTS

Solve exercises, add code errors, and ask classmate to find them

ANTI-PATTERN GENERAL DATA

ID	TITLE			
C_IF1	Missing "&" in front of variable in "scanf"			
EXAMPLE:				
<div style="display: flex; align-items: center; justify-content: center;"> 8 scanf("%d", numero); </div>				
ERROR TYPE:				
	Syntax	X	Semantics	Style
CONTENT:				
- Variable - Data input function				
IN WHAT LANGUAGE WAS THE MISTAKE MADE?				
	X	C		Python
PROBLEM:				
The C programming language requires "&" in front of the variable to indicate that the value that the user types as input will be stored in the address of the variable. Failure to do so will generate a runtime error, causing the program not to execute appropriately.				
CONNECTIONS TO OTHER ANTI-PATTERNS:				
- C_IF2 – Missing quotes in the input function call - C_IF6 – Missing “,” to separate first from second parameter in “scanf”				
EVENTS				
Note: In the code snippets presented below, only the anti-pattern question of this table was analyzed. If other errors exist, these errors have been handled in other anti-patterns.				
EVENT 1				
Student Id: 2257		Total of submissions of the exercise:		6
The exercise that was being solved:				
Exercise 1.1				
Error		Fixed Error		
<div style="display: flex; align-items: center; justify-content: center;"> 8 scanf("%d", numero); </div>		Tentativa 1: <div style="display: flex; align-items: center; justify-content: center;"> 8 scanf("%d"; numero); </div> Final <div style="display: flex; align-items: center; justify-content: center;"> 8 scanf("%d", &numero); </div>		
Occurred in submission: 1		Fixed on submission: 4		
Observation: The error occurs during program execution.		Observation: Before reaching this result, she/he tried to put “;” (semicolon) in place of the comma inside the parentheses.		
EVENT 2				
Student Id: 2670		Total of submissions of the exercise:		4
The exercise that was being solved:				
Exercise 1.1				
Error		Fixed Error		
<div style="display: flex; align-items: center; justify-content: center;"> 3 scanf("%d", a); </div>		<div style="display: flex; align-items: center; justify-content: center;"> 3 scanf("%d", &a); </div>		

Occurred in submission: 1 Observation:	Fixed on submission: 2 Observation:
EVENT 3	
Student Id: 2719	Total of submissions of the exercise: 3
The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 1.1	
Error	Fixed Error
7 scanf("%d", num);	7 scanf("%d", &num);
Occurred in submission: 1 Observation:	Fixed on submission: 3 Observation:
EVENT 4	
Student Id: 1781	Total of submissions of the exercise: 3
The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 2.1	
Error	Fixed Error
5 scanf("%d,%d", a, b);	5 scanf("%d,%d", &a, &b);
Occurred in submission: 1 Observation:	Fixed on submission: 2 Observation: Other errors persist.
A SUGGESTED SOLUTION	
FOR PROFESSORS	
Explanation using blackboard and projector – reinforce the concept using Kahoot	
FOR STUDENTS	
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ANTI-PATTERN GENERAL DATA

ID	TITLE					
C_IF6	Missing “,” to separate first from second parameter in “scanf”					
EXAMPLE:						
<div style="display: flex; align-items: center; justify-content: center;"> 4 <pre style="color: #000080; font-family: monospace;">scanf("%d %d" a,b);</pre> </div>						
ERROR TYPE:						
	X	Syntax		Semantics		Style
CONTENT:						
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data input function - Function: parameter declaration 						
IN WHAT LANGUAGE WAS THE MISTAKE MADE?						
	X	C				Python
PROBLEM:						
This error prevents the program from running because, by the language rules, the parameters must be separated by a comma.						
CONNECTIONS TO OTHER ANTI-PATTERNS:						
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - C_IF1 – Missing "&" in front of variable in "scanf" - C_IF2 – Missing quotes in the input function call - C_F9 – Incorrect declaration of function parameters 						
EVENTS						
<p>Note: In the code snippets presented below, only the anti-pattern question of this table was analyzed. If other errors exist, these errors have been handled in other anti-patterns.</p>						
EVENT 1						
Student Id: 2040		Total of submissions of the exercise:				7
The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 2.1						
Error <div style="display: flex; align-items: center; justify-content: center;"> 4 <pre style="color: #000080; font-family: monospace;">scanf("%d %d" a,b);</pre> </div> <p>Occurred in submission: 1 Observation: The comma between the two "%d" will cause the program to stop executing reading the data, which means the program will not run properly.</p>				Fixed Error <div style="display: flex; align-items: center; justify-content: center;"> 5 <pre style="color: #000080; font-family: monospace;">scanf("%d %d", a,b);</pre> </div> <p>Fixed on submission: 6 Observation:</p>		
EVENT 2						
Student Id: 3167		Total of submissions of the exercise:				7
The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 3.1						
Error <div style="display: flex; align-items: center; justify-content: center;"> 6 <pre style="color: #000080; font-family: monospace;">scanf ("%d%d%d" &a1, &a2, &a3);</pre> </div> <p>Occurred in submission: 1</p>				Fixed Error <div style="display: flex; align-items: center; justify-content: center;"> 6 <pre style="color: #000080; font-family: monospace;">scanf ("%d%d%d", &a1, &a2, &a3);</pre> </div> <p>Fixed on submission: 2</p>		

Observation:	Observation:
EVENT 3	
Student Id: 2810	Total of submissions of the exercise: 2
The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 3.1	
Error	Fixed Error
7 <code>scanf("%d %d %d" &x, &y, &z);</code>	7 <code>scanf("%d %d %d", &x, &y, &z);</code>
Occurred in submission: 1 Observation:	Fixed on submission: 2 Observation:
EVENT 4	
Student Id:	Total of submissions of the exercise:
The exercise that was being solved:	
Error	Fixed Error
Occurred in submission: Observation:	Fixed on submission: Observation:
A SUGGESTED SOLUTION	
FOR PROFESSORS	
Explanation using blackboard and projector – reinforce the concept using Kahoot	
FOR STUDENTS	
Solve exercises, add code errors, and ask classmate to find them	

ANTI-PATTERN GENERAL DATA

ID	TITLE			
C_OF1	Improper use of "&" in front of variable in "printf"			
EXAMPLE:				
<pre>5 printf("%d",&a);</pre>				
ERROR TYPE:				
	Syntax	X	Semantics	Style
CONTENT:				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Variable - Data Output Function - Function: passing parameter by reference 				
IN WHAT LANGUAGE WAS THE MISTAKE MADE?				
	X	C		Python
PROBLEM:				
The program will run, but the result will not be the expected as the address of the variable instead of the value stored inside it will be printed.				
CONNECTIONS TO OTHER ANTI-PATTERNS:				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - C_OF2 – Wrong spelling of “printf” command - C_OF3 – Missing quotation mark in output function - C_OF4 – Use of "&" instead of "%" in “printf” - C_OF5 – Parameter identifying incorrect or non-existent output data type - C_OF6 – Missing comma to separate parameters in data output function 				
EVENTS				
Note: In the code snippets presented below, only the anti-pattern question of this table was analyzed. If other errors exist, these errors have been handled in other anti-patterns.				
EVENT 1				
Student Id: 1781		Total of submissions of the exercise:		2
The exercise that was being solved:				
Exercise 1.1				
Error		Fixed Error		
<pre>5 printf("%d",&a);</pre>		<pre>5 printf("%d",a);</pre>		
Occurred in submission: 1		Fixed on submission: 2		
Observation:		Observation:		
EVENT 2				
Student Id: 2257		Total of submissions of the exercise:		6
The exercise that was being solved:				
Exercise 1.1				
Error		Fixed Error		
<pre>9 printf("0 numero digitado foi o %d."; &numero);</pre>		<pre>9 printf("0 numero digitado foi o %d.", numero);</pre>		
Occurred in submission: 4		Fixed on submission: 5		
Observation:		Observation:		

EVENT 3		
Student Id: 3167	Total of submissions of the exercise:	8
The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 1.1		
Error		Fixed Error
5 L <code>printf("%d", &b);}</code>		5 L <code>printf("%d", b);}</code>
Occurred in submission: 5 Observation:		Fixed on submission: 8 Observation:
EVENT 4		
Student Id: 1830	Total of submissions of the exercise:	6
The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 7.1		
Error		Fixed Error
9 <code>printf("%f", &soma);</code>		9 <code>printf("%f", soma);</code>
Occurred in submission: 3 Observation:		Fixed on submission: 4 Observation:
A SUGGESTED SOLUTION		
FOR PROFESSORS		
Explanation using blackboard and projector – reinforce the concept using Kahoot		
FOR STUDENTS		
Solve exercises, add code errors, and ask classmate to find them		

ANTI-PATTERN GENERAL DATA

ID	TITLE		
C_OF3	Wrong spelling of "printf" command		
EXAMPLE:			
<pre>7 print(" %d " , num);</pre>			
ERROR TYPE:	X	Syntax	Semantics
CONTENT:	- Data Output Function		
IN WHAT LANGUAGE WAS THE MISTAKE MADE?	X	C	Python
PROBLEM:			
The compiler does not recognize the command name and thus does not know what to do. The error message says that the identifier was not created in the current scope.			
CONNECTIONS TO OTHER ANTI-PATTERNS:			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - C_OF1 – Improper use of "&" in front of variable in "printf" - C_OF3 – Missing quotation mark in output function - C_OF4 – Use of "&" instead of "%" in "printf" - C_OF5 – Parameter identifying incorrect or non-existent output data type - C_OF6 – Missing comma to separate parameters in data output function 			
EVENTS			
<p>Note: In the code snippets presented below, only the anti-pattern question of this table was analyzed. If other errors exist, these errors have been handled in other anti-patterns.</p>			
EVENT 1			
Student Id: 2243		Total of submissions of the exercise: 3	
The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 1.1			
Error		Fixed Error	
<pre>7 print(" %d " , num);</pre>		<pre>7 printf(" %d " , num);</pre>	
Occurred in submission: 2		Fixed on submission: 3	
Observation:		Observation:	
EVENT 2			
Student Id: 3430		Total of submissions of the exercise: 7	
The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 1.1			
Error		Fixed Error	
<pre>7 printf("%d", &n);</pre>		<pre>7 printf("%d", &n);</pre>	
Occurred in submission: 1		Fixed on submission: 2	
Observation:		Observation:	
EVENT 3			
Student Id: 3300		Total of submissions of the exercise: 4	

The exercise that was being solved:
Exercise 3.1

Error

```
15 | print("SIM %d %d %d", a, b, c);
```

Occurred in submission: 1
Observation:

Fixed Error

```
15 | printf("SIM %d %d %d", a, b, c);
```

Fixed on submission: 2
Observation:

EVENT 4

Student Id: 5242

Total of submissions of the exercise:

62

The exercise that was being solved:
Exercise 3.3

Error

```
11 | print ( soma )
```

Occurred in submission: 8
Observation:

Fixed Error

Fixed on submission:
Observation: The error has not been fixed.

A SUGGESTED SOLUTION

FOR PROFESSORS

Explanation using blackboard and projector – reinforce the concept using Kahoot

FOR STUDENTS

Solve exercises, add code errors, and ask classmate to find them

ANTI-PATTERN GENERAL DATA

ID	TITLE		
C_OF5	Parameter identifying incorrect or non-existent output data type		
EXAMPLE:			
<div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 5px; display: inline-block;"> 7 printf(a); </div>			
ERROR TYPE:			
X	Syntax	Semantics	Style
CONTENT: - Data Output Function			
IN WHAT LANGUAGE WAS THE MISTAKE MADE?			
X	C	Python	
PROBLEM:			
The compiler expects to find the parameter that identifies the type of data to be printed, and missing this information generates a syntax error that causes the program not to execute.			
CONNECTIONS TO OTHER ANTI-PATTERNS:			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - C_OF1 – Improper use of "&" in front of variable in "printf" - C_OF2 – Wrong spelling of "printf" command - C_OF3 – Missing quotation mark in output function - C_OF4 – Use of "&" instead of "%" in "printf" - C_OF6 – Missing comma to separate parameters in data output function 			
EVENTS			
Note: In the code snippets presented below, only the anti-pattern question of this table was analyzed. If other errors exist, these errors have been handled in other anti-patterns.			
EVENT 1			
Student Id: 2040		Total of submissions of the exercise: 8	
The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 2.1			
Error <div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 5px; display: inline-block;"> 7 printf(a); </div> Occurred in submission: 1 Observation:	Fixed Error <div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 5px; display: inline-block;"> 10 printf("%d",a); </div> Fixed on submission: 7 Observation:		
EVENT 2			
Student Id: 5730		Total of submissions of the exercise: 11	
The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 2.1			
Error <div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 5px; display: inline-block;"> 6 printf("n1",n1); </div> Occurred in submission: 1 Observation: Failed to identify the type of output data, which should be "%d" since "n1" is of type "int".	Fixed Error <div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 5px; display: inline-block;"> 6 printf("%d",n1); </div> Fixed on submission: 2 Observation:		

EVENT 3		
Student Id: 5242	Total of submissions of the exercise:	62
The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 3.3		
Error		Fixed Error
<pre>11 print (soma)</pre>		
<p>Occurred in submission: 8 Observation: The variable “soma” is of type “int”, so “%d” was missing, followed by a comma, before the variable. It is noteworthy that the command name “printf” is spelled wrong.</p>		<p>Fixed on submission: Observation: In the 16th submission, the student erases this "printf" line, solving the problem without solving the error.</p>
EVENT 4		
Student Id: 3430	Total of submissions of the exercise:	4
The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 7.1		
Error		Fixed Error
<pre>5 float soma = 0.0; ... 14 printf("%d/n", soma);</pre>		<pre>16 printf("%f", soma);</pre>
<p>Occurred in submission: 1 Observation: Line 5 shows the student declaring the variable “soma” as “float”, but she or he used “%d” to print the value instead of “%f”.</p>		<p>Fixed on submission: 3 Observation:</p>
A SUGGESTED SOLUTION		
FOR PROFESSORS		
Groups working with step-by-step execution to understand errors – reinforce with exercises		
FOR STUDENTS		
Solve exercises, add code errors, and ask classmate to find them		

ANTI-PATTERN GENERAL DATA

ID	TITLE		
C_OF6	Use of "&" instead of "%" in "printf"		
EXAMPLE:			
<div style="display: flex; align-items: center; justify-content: center;"> 7 <pre style="margin: 0;">printf("&d", a);</pre> </div>			
ERROR TYPE:			
	Syntax	X	Semantics
CONTENT: - Data Output Function			
IN WHAT LANGUAGE WAS THE MISTAKE MADE?			
	X	C	Python
PROBLEM:			
The program will run, but will not show the value stored in the variable.			
CONNECTIONS TO OTHER ANTI-PATTERNS:			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - C_OF1 – Improper use of "&" in front of variable in "printf" - C_OF2 – Wrong spelling of "printf" command - C_OF3 – Missing quotation mark in output function - C_OF5 – Parameter identifying incorrect or non-existent output data type - C_OF6 – Missing comma to separate parameters in data output function 			
EVENTS			
<p>Note: In the code snippets presented below, only the anti-pattern question of this table was analyzed. If other errors exist, these errors have been handled in other anti-patterns.</p>			
EVENT 1			
Student Id: 3139		Total of submissions of the exercise: 7	
The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 1.1			
Error <div style="display: flex; align-items: center; justify-content: center;"> 7 <pre style="margin: 0;">printf("&d", a);</pre> </div>		Fixed Error Attempt (Tentativa) 1: <div style="display: flex; align-items: center; justify-content: center;"> 7 <pre style="margin: 0;">printf("10", a);</pre> </div> Final (Final): <div style="display: flex; align-items: center; justify-content: center;"> 7 <pre style="margin: 0;">printf("%d", a);</pre> </div>	
Occurred in submission: 2 Observation:		Fixed on submission: 5 Observation:	
EVENT 2			
Student Id: 2257		Total of submissions of the exercise: 2	
The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 1.2			
Error <div style="display: flex; align-items: center; justify-content: center;"> 8 <pre style="margin: 0;">printf("&d", numero*numero);</pre> </div>		Fixed Error <div style="display: flex; align-items: center; justify-content: center;"> 8 <pre style="margin: 0;">printf("%d", numero*numero);</pre> </div>	
Occurred in submission: 1		Fixed on submission: 2	

Observation:	Observation:
EVENT 3	
Student Id: 2950	Total of submissions of the exercise: 8
The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 1.2	
Error	Fixed Error
5 <code>printf("&d", n*n);</code>	5 <code>printf("%d", n*n);</code>
Occurred in submission: 1 Observation:	Fixed on submission: 8 Observation:
EVENT 4	
Student Id:	Total of submissions of the exercise:
The exercise that was being solved:	
Error	Fixed Error
Occurred in submission: Observation:	Fixed on submission: Observation:
A SUGGESTED SOLUTION	
FOR PROFESSORS	
Explanation using blackboard and projector – reinforce the concept using Kahoot	
FOR STUDENTS	
Solve exercises, add code errors, and ask classmate to find them	

ANTI-PATTERN GENERAL DATA

ID	TITLE
C_OF7	Result not presented to the user

EXAMPLE:

7	<code>while(soma <= num)</code>
8	<code>{</code>
9	<code>soma += soma++;</code>
10	<code>}</code>
11	<code>return 0;</code>

ERROR TYPE:	Syntax	X	Semantics	Style
CONTENT:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - General - Data Output Function 			
IN WHAT LANGUAGE WAS THE MISTAKE MADE?	X	C	Python	

PROBLEM:

The program will run, but the result will not be presented to the user.

CONNECTIONS TO OTHER ANTI-PATTERNS:

EVENTS

Note: In the code snippets presented below, only the anti-pattern question of this table was analyzed. If other errors exist, these errors have been handled in other anti-patterns.

EVENT 1

Student Id: 2243	Total of submissions of the exercise:	11
The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 3.3		
<p>Error</p>	<p>Occurred in submission: 2</p> <p>Fixed on submission: 11</p> <p>Observation:</p>	

EVENT 2

Student Id: 1963	Total of submissions of the exercise:	12
The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 4.1		
<p>Error</p>	<p>Fixed Error</p>	

```

3 int main (void) {
4     int n1, n2;
5     scanf("%d %d", &n1, &n2);
6     soma(n1, n2);
7     media(n1, n2);
8 }

```

Occurred in submission: 1
Observation:

```

3 int main (void) {
4     int n1, n2;
5     scanf("%d %d", &n1, &n2);
6     printf("%d", soma(n1, n2));
7     printf("%f", media(n1, n2));
8 }

```

Fixed on submission: 2
Observation:

EVENT 3

Student Id: 1781 Total of submissions of the exercise: 6

The exercise that was being solved:
Exercise 7.2

Error

```

7 while(n>0)
8 {
9     y=x*x;
10    n--;
11 }
12 return 0;
13 }

```

Occurred in submission: 1
Observation: The result calculated within the repetition was not presented to the user. PS: The formula in this code is wrong.

Fixed Error

```

8 while(n>0)
9 {
10    y=x*x;
11    n--;
12 }
13 printf("%d",y);

```

Fixed on submission: 3
Observation:

EVENT 4

Student Id: 2061 Total of submissions of the exercise: 6

The exercise that was being solved:
Exercise 8.1

Error

```

14 int main () {
15     int n, i, r, vet[40];
16     scanf("%d", &n);
17     for(i=0; i<n; i++) {
18         scanf("%d", &vet[i]);
19     }
20     r=determineSeOrdenado(n, vet[]);
21     return 0;
22 }

```

Occurred in submission: 1
Observation:

Fixed Error

```

20 r=determineSeOrdenado(n, vet[]);
21 printf("%d", r);
22 return 0;
23 }

```

Fixed on submission: 2
Observation:

A SUGGESTED SOLUTION FOR PROFESSORS

Programming in front of the students, making the error appear – reinforce by asking students to develop new codes

FOR STUDENTS

Study one or more anti-patterns, introduce to classmate and reinforce with exercise

<p>Occurred in submission: 1 Observation:</p>	<p>Fixed on submission: 8 Observation:</p>
EVENT 2	
<p>Student Id: 4930</p>	<p>Total of submissions of the exercise: 9</p>
<p>The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 4.1</p>	
<p style="text-align: center;">Error</p> <pre> 20 res = (a+b/2); </pre> <p>Occurred in submission: 3 Observation: The result generated by the operation on line 20 will be a value of type "int." For the division to generate a "float" result, the divisor should be "2.0" or "(float)" should precede "(a + b)" to cast the operand (misuse of parentheses is another error dealt with in another table).</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Fixed Error</p> <p style="text-align: center;">?</p> <p>Fixed on submission: Observation: The error has not been fixed.</p>
EVENT 3	
<p>Student Id: 2061</p>	<p>Total of submissions of the exercise: 6</p>
<p>The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 4.1</p>	
<p style="text-align: center;">Error</p> <pre> 8 float M; 9 M=(a+b)/2; </pre> <p>Occurred in submission: 3 Observation: This division generates a result of type "int" instead of "float."</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Fixed Error</p> <pre> 8 float M; 9 M=(a+b)/2.0; </pre> <p>Fixed on submission: 6 Observation:</p>
EVENT 4	
<p>Student Id: 3139</p>	<p>Total of submissions of the exercise: 6</p>
<p>The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 7.1</p>	
<p style="text-align: center;">Error</p> <pre> 5 int n, soma = 0; 6 scanf("%d", &n); 7 while (n >= 1){ 8 soma = soma + 1/n; 9 n--; 10 } 11 12 printf("%d", soma); </pre> <p>Occurred in submission: 3 Observation: Line 8 shows variables "sum"</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Fixed Error</p> <pre> 5 float n = 0.0, soma = 0.0; 6 scanf("%f", &n); 7 for (float i = 1.0; i <= n; i++){ 8 soma = soma + 1.0/i; 9 } 10 11 printf("%f", soma); </pre> <p>Fixed on submission: 6 Observation: The student solved the problem</p>

and "n" being declared as "int," however, the result stored in sum should be of type "float." Apart from making a mistake in the declaration, merely doing this division would not generate a float value in the variable "soma."

by declaring all variables as "float."

A SUGGESTED SOLUTION

FOR PROFESSORS

Programming in front of the students, making the error appear – reinforce by asking students to develop new codes

FOR STUDENTS

Study one or more anti-patterns, introduce to classmate and reinforce with exercise

ANTI-PATTERN GENERAL DATA

ID	TITLE			
C_AE2	Wrong arithmetic formula			
EXAMPLE:				
<pre> 18 □ double media(int a, int b){ 19 return (a+b/2); 20 } </pre>				
ERROR TYPE:				
	Syntax	X	Semantics	Style
CONTENT:				
- Arithmetic Expression				
IN WHAT LANGUAGE WAS THE MISTAKE MADE?				
	X	C		Python
PROBLEM:				
Respecting the order of the operations is critical to generate a correct result. As written, the calculus will not be done in the desired order, i.e., first the sum and then the division.				
CONNECTIONS TO OTHER ANTI-PATTERNS:				
- C AE1 – Float result type in integer division				
EVENTS				
Note: In the code snippets presented below, only the anti-pattern question of this table was analyzed. If other errors exist, these errors have been handled in other anti-patterns.				
EVENT 1				
Student Id: 4770		Total of submissions of the exercise:		13
The exercise that was being solved:				
Exercise 4.1				
Error		Fixed Error		
<pre> 18 □ double media(int a, int b){ 19 return (a+b/2); 20 } </pre>		<pre> 6 □ float media(int a, int b){ 7 return((a+b)/2.0) 8 } </pre>		
Occurred in submission: 1		Fixed on submission: 12		
Observation: To calculate the average, the sum should be in parentheses; otherwise, the division will be done first.		Observation:		
EVENT 2				
Student Id: 4930		Total of submissions of the exercise:		9
The exercise that was being solved:				
Exercise 4.1				
Error		Fixed Error		
<pre> 20 res = (a+b/2); </pre>		<pre> 21 res = (a+b)/2; </pre>		
Occurred in submission: 3		Fixed on submission: 5		
Observation:		Observation:		

EVENT 3

Student Id: 2243

Total of submissions of the exercise:

5

The exercise that was being solved:
Exercise 4.1**Error**

```
10 | return a+b/2.0;
```

Occurred in submission: 2
Observation:

Fixed Error

```
10 | return (a+b)/2.0;
```

Fixed on submission: 3
Observation:

EVENT 4

Student Id: 1781

Total of submissions of the exercise:

6

The exercise that was being solved:
Exercise 7.2**Error**

```
4 | int x,n,y;
5 | y=0;
6 | scanf("%d%d",&x,&n);
7 | while(n>0)
8 | {
9 |     y=x*x;
10 |     n--;
11 | }
```

Occurred in submission: 1
Observation: The goal was to do x^n , so “y” would accumulate the results of the multiplications, but this is not happening.

Fixed Error

```
4 | int x;
5 | float n,y;
6 | y=1;
7 | scanf("%d%f",&x,&n);
8 | while(x>0)
9 | {
10 |     y=y*n;
11 |     x--;
12 | }
```

Fixed on submission: 6
Observation:

**A SUGGESTED SOLUTION
FOR PROFESSORS**

Programming in front of the students, making the error appear – reinforce by asking students to develop new codes

FOR STUDENTS

Study one or more anti-patterns, introduce to classmate and reinforce with exercise

ANTI-PATTERN GENERAL DATA

ID	TITLE			
C_AE3	Calculation performed before having values in the used variables			
EXAMPLE:				
<pre> 3 int a,b,c,d; 4 d = a+b+c; 5 scanf("%d%d%d",&a,&b,&c); </pre>				
ERROR TYPE:	Syntax	X	Semantics	Style
CONTENT:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - General: Execution Order - Variable - Data input function - Arithmetic Expression 			
IN WHAT LANGUAGE WAS THE MISTAKE MADE?	X	C		Python
PROBLEM:				
The sum was performed (line 4) before the values were typed by the user (line 5).				
CONNECTIONS TO OTHER ANTI-PATTERNS:				
EVENTS				
<p>Note: In the code snippets presented below, only the anti-pattern question of this table was analyzed. If other errors exist, these errors have been handled in other anti-patterns.</p>				
EVENT 1				
Student Id: 1781		Total of submissions of the exercise:		5
The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 3.1				
Error		Fixed Error		
<pre> 4 d = a+b+c; 5 scanf("%d%d%d",&a,&b,&c); </pre>		<pre> 4 scanf("%d%d%d",&a,&b,&c); 5 if(a+b+c == 180){ </pre>		
Occurred in submission: 1 Observation: Lines 4 and 5 should be reversed.		Fixed on submission: 2 Observation:		
EVENT 2				
Student Id: 5098		Total of submissions of the exercise:		12
The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 3.1				
Error		Fixed Error		
<pre> 3 int a,b,c,soma; 4 soma=a+b+c; 5 scanf("%d %d %d", &a, &b, &c); </pre>		<pre> 3 int a,b,c,soma; 4 scanf("%d %d %d", &a, &b, &c); 5 soma = a+b+c; </pre>		

Occurred in submission: 5
Observation:

Fixed on submission: 12
Observation:

EVENT 3

Student Id: 5226

Total of submissions of the exercise:

11

The exercise that was being solved:
Exercise 3.3

Error

```
1 int main(){
2     int n, cont,x;
3     cont =0;
4     printf("");
5     scanf("%d", n);
6     while(n > cont) {
7
8         cont = cont +1 ;
9         x = x + cont;
10
11     }
12     printf("%d", x);
13     return 0 ;
14 }
```

Occurred in submission: 7

Observation: The sum operation on line 9 used the variable "x," but without assigning value to it.

Fixed Error

```
1 int main(){
2     int n, contador,total;
3     printf("");
4     scanf("%d", n);
5     while(contador = 0, total = 0; n > total; contador += 1 ){
6         total += contador;
7     }
8     printf("%d", total);
9     return 0 ;
10 }
```

Fixed on submission: 8

Observation: Operation deleted on the next submission, but other errors arose. These new errors will be addressed in other tables.

EVENT 4

Student Id: 1963

Total of submissions of the exercise:

4

The exercise that was being solved:
Exercise 7.2

Error

```
3 int main (void) {
4     int n, i;
5     float x, res = 1;
6     scanf("%d", n);
7
8     for(i=1;i<n;i++)
9         res = res * x;
```

Occurred in submission: 1

Observation: The multiplication operation on line 9 uses variable "x," but without assigning value to it.

Fixed Error

```
3 int main (void) {
4     int n, i;
5     float x, res = 1;
6     scanf("%d", &n);
7     scanf("%f", &x);
8
9     for (i=1;i<n;i++)
10        res = res * x;
```

Fixed on submission: 2

Observation: "Scanf" has been added to initialize the variable "x" used in line 7.

A SUGGESTED SOLUTION FOR PROFESSORS

Groups working with step-by-step execution to understand errors – reinforce with exercises

FOR STUDENTS

Introduce the error into a code and understand the consequences it generates

ANTI-PATTERN GENERAL DATA

ID	TITLE		
C_RE5	Comparison performed before having values in the used variables		
EXAMPLE:			
<pre> 3 int a,b; 4 if(a<b){ </pre>			
ERROR TYPE:	Syntax	X	Semantics
CONTENT:	- Variable - Relational Expression		
IN WHAT LANGUAGE WAS THE MISTAKE MADE?	X	C	Python
PROBLEM:			
The comparison will be made with so-called "memory junk", unknown and uncontrolled values.			
CONNECTIONS TO OTHER ANTI-PATTERNS:			
EVENTS			
Note: In the code snippets presented below, only the anti-pattern question of this table was analyzed. If other errors exist, these errors have been handled in other anti-patterns.			
EVENT 1			
Student Id: 1781		Total of submissions of the exercise: 5	
The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 2.2			
<p style="text-align: center;">Error</p> <pre> 3 int a,b; 4 if(a<b){ </pre> <p>Occurred in submission: 2 Observation: In line 3 the variables "a" and "b" are declared without value assignment and in the next line, they are already compared.</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Fixed Error</p> <pre> 3 int a,b; 4 scanf ("%d,%d",&a,&b); 5 if(a<b){ </pre> <p>Fixed on submission: 3 Observation:</p>		
EVENT 2			
Student Id: 2243		Total of submissions of the exercise: 3	
The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 3.2			
<p style="text-align: center;">Error</p> <pre> 5 int n1, n2, n3; 6 if(n1*n1 == n2*n2 + n3*n3) printf("1"); </pre> <p>Occurred in submission: 1 Observation:</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Fixed Error</p> <pre> 5 int n1, n2, n3; 6 scanf("%d%d%d", &n1, &n2, &n3); 7 if(n1*n1 == n2*n2 + n3*n3) printf("1"); </pre> <p>Fixed on submission: 2 Observation:</p>		

EVENT 3

Student Id: 1830

Total of submissions of the exercise:

6

The exercise that was being solved:

Exercise 3.1

Error

```

3 |
4 | int n;
5 | float soma=0.0;
  | while(n>0){
  |

```

Occurred in submission: 3

Observation:

Fixed Error

```

3 | int n;
4 | float soma=0.0;
5 | scanf("%d", &n);
6 | while(n>0){
  |

```

Fixed on submission: 6

Observation:

EVENT 4

Student Id:

Total of submissions of the exercise:

The exercise that was being solved:

Error

Occurred in submission:

Observation:

Fixed Error

Fixed on submission:

Observation:

A SUGGESTED SOLUTION**FOR PROFESSORS**

Groups working with step-by-step execution to understand errors – reinforce with exercises

FOR STUDENTS

Introduce the error into a code and understand the consequences it generates


```

2  |
3  |   int main(){
4  |       int b, a;
5  |       scanf("%d %d",&b, &a);
6  |       if(b>a){printf("%d",b);}
   |       else {printf("%d",a);}

```

Occurred in submission: 1
Observation:

```

2  |   int main(){
3  |       int b, a;
4  |       scanf("%d %d",&b, &a);
5  |       if(b>a){printf("%d",b);}
6  |       else {printf("%d",a);}}

```

Fixed on submission: 2
Observation:

EVENT 3

Student Id: 1830 Total of submissions of the exercise: 5

The exercise that was being solved:
Exercise 2.2

Error

```

5  |   if(a<b){
6  |       res==1;
7  |   }
8  |   else{
9  |       res==0;
10 |   }

```

Occurred in submission: 3
Observation:

Fixed Error

```

5  |   if(a<b){
6  |       res==1;
7  |   }
8  |   else{
9  |       res==0;
10 |   }

```

Fixed on submission: 4
Observation:

EVENT 4

Student Id: Total of submissions of the exercise:

The exercise that was being solved:

Error

Fixed Error

Occurred in submission:
Observation:

Fixed on submission:
Observation:

A SUGGESTED SOLUTION

FOR PROFESSORS

Programming in front of the students, making the error appear – reinforce by asking students to develop new codes

FOR STUDENTS

Study one or more anti-patterns, introduce to classmate and reinforce with exercise

ANTI-PATTERN GENERAL DATA

ID	TITLE
C_SS4	Improper “;” after “if” condition and/or after “else”

EXAMPLE:

```

9 | if num1 > num2;
10 |     printf("%d", num1);
    
```

ERROR TYPE:	X	Syntax	X	Semantics		Style
--------------------	---	--------	---	-----------	--	-------

CONTENT:
 - General
 - Selection Structure

IN WHAT LANGUAGE WAS THE MISTAKE MADE?	X	C		Python
---	---	---	--	--------

PROBLEM:

The semicolon right after the selection condition will cause it to end exactly at that point, and commands that should only be executed if the condition were true will execute regardless of the response. The same goes for "else". However, if a semicolon is placed after the "if" condition and it has an "else" associated with it, a compilation error occurs, meaning that the code will not be executed.

CONNECTIONS TO OTHER ANTI-PATTERNS:

- C G2 – Missing “;” at end of line

EVENTS

Note: In the code snippets presented below, only the anti-pattern question of this table was analyzed. If other errors exist, these errors have been handled in other anti-patterns.

EVENT 1

Student Id: 5098	Total of submissions of the exercise:	20
-------------------------	--	----

The exercise that was being solved:
 Exercise 2.1

Error

```

9 | if num1 > num2;
10 |     printf("%d", num1);
11 |
12 | if num2 >= num1;
13 |     printf("%d", num2);
    
```

Occurred in submission: 1
Observation:

Fixed Error

```

7 | if (num1>=num2){
8 |     printf("%d", num1);
9 | }
10 | else{
11 |     printf("%d", num2);
12 | }
    
```

Fixed on submission: 19
Observation:

EVENT 2

Student Id: 5730	Total of submissions of the exercise:	11
-------------------------	--	----

The exercise that was being solved:
 Exercise 2.1

Error

Fixed Error

<pre> 5 if n1>n2; 6 printf("n1",n1); 7 else; 8 printf("n2",n2); </pre>	<pre> 5 if (n1>n2) 6 printf("%d",n1); 7 else 8 printf("%d",n2); </pre>
<p>Occurred in submission: 1 Observation:</p>	<p>Fixed on submission: 8 Observation:</p>
EVENT 3	
<p>Student Id: 2901</p>	<p>Total of submissions of the exercise: 10</p>
<p>The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 3.1</p>	
<p style="text-align: center;">Error</p> <pre> 17 if(soma>180) 18 printf("NAO %d", soma) 19 else if(soma == 180) 20 printf("Sim %d %d %d", 21 else if("soma<180"); 22 printf("NAO %d", soma) </pre>	<p style="text-align: center;">Fixed Error</p> <pre> 17 if(soma>180) 18 printf("NAO %d", soma); 19 else{ 20 if (soma==180) 21 printf("Sim %d %d %d", a,b,c); 22 else 23 printf("NAO %d", soma); 24 25 } </pre>
<p>Occurred in submission: 3 Observation: The "if" of line 21 has a semicolon at the end of the parentheses of the condition, causing the structure to be improperly terminated at that point.</p>	<p>Fixed on submission: 9 Observation: Because it is unnecessary, the "if" with the semicolon was eliminated in the penultimate submission.</p>
EVENT 4	
<p>Student Id:</p>	<p>Total of submissions of the exercise:</p>
<p>The exercise that was being solved:</p>	
<p style="text-align: center;">Error</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Fixed Error</p>
<p>Occurred in submission: Observation:</p>	<p>Fixed on submission: Observation:</p>
A SUGGESTED SOLUTION	
FOR PROFESSORS	
Explanation using blackboard and projector – reinforce the concept using Kahoot	
FOR STUDENTS	
Introduce the error into a code and understand the consequences it generates	

ANTI-PATTERN GENERAL DATA

ID	TITLE
C_RS3	Result printed in wrong place

EXAMPLE:

```

14 while (soma < total){
15
16
17     soma = soma + i;
18
19     i = i + 1;
20     printf ("%d", soma);
21
22 }
23
24     printf ("%d", soma);
    
```

ERROR TYPE:	Syntax	X	Semantics	Style
CONTENT:	- Data Output Function - Repetition Structure: while			
IN WHAT LANGUAGE WAS THE MISTAKE MADE?	X	C	Python	

PROBLEM:

In some cases, it may occur that the result is displayed inside the repetition. However, in this case, it is wrong because it is an intermediate result and, being inside the repetition, all of such intermediate results will be shown”.

CONNECTIONS TO OTHER ANTI-PATTERNS:

- C OF7 – Result not presented to the user

EVENTS

Note: In the code snippets presented below, only the anti-pattern question of this table was analyzed. If other errors exist, these errors have been handled in other anti-patterns.

EVENT 1

Student Id: 5906	Total of submissions of the exercise:	3
The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 3.3		

Error

Fixed Error

```

14 while (soma < total){
15
16
17     soma = soma + i;
18
19     i = i + 1;
20     printf ("%d", soma);
21
22 }
23
24 printf ("%d", soma);

```

Occurred in submission: 1
Observation: The "printf" that is inside the loop will make the intermediate result to be printed out every repetition, even though it is not the final result.

```

14 while (soma <= total) {
15
16
17     soma = soma + i;
18
19     i = i + 1;
20
21
22 }
23
24 printf ("%d", soma - i + 1);

```

Fixed on submission: 2
Observation: The "printf" has been deleted from the loop (line 20), thus correcting the error.

EVENT 2

Student Id: 5730 **Total of submissions of the exercise:** 59

The exercise that was being solved:
Exercise 3.3

Error

```

7 while i<=n {
8     soma=i+1
9     i=i+1
10    printf("%d", soma);
11 }

```

Occurred in submission: 1
Observation: With "printf" on line 10, the result was printed on each repetition rather than presented only at the end.

Fixed Error

```

11 while (soma<=n) {
12     soma=soma+1;
13     i=i+1;
14 }
15 printf("%d\n", soma);

```

Fixed on submission: 10
Observation: The "printf" was taken from inside the loop and placed outside in line 15.

EVENT 3

Student Id: 5242 **Total of submissions of the exercise:** 62

The exercise that was being solved:
Exercise 3.3

Error

```

9 while ( soma <= num ){
10     soma = num + 1 ;
11     print ( soma )
12 }

```

Occurred in submission: 8
Observation:

Fixed Error

Fixed on submission:
Observation:

EVENT 4

Student Id: 1830 **Total of submissions of the exercise:** 12

The exercise that was being solved:
Exercise 4.7

Error

Fixed Error

```

3 | int n, i=0, soma=0, numero;
4 | scanf("%d", &n);
5 | while(i<n){
6 |     while(numero!=0){
7 |         if(numero%2!=0){
8 |             soma=soma+numero;
9 |         }
10 |     }
11 |     i++;
12 | }
13 | printf("%d", soma);

```

Occurred in submission: 3

Observation: The exercise asks to show the sum of all odd numbers of each of the n subsequences, i.e., "printf" should be right after the internal repeating structure closes.

```

6 | while(i<n){
7 |     while(numero!=0){
8 |         if(numero%2!=0){
9 |             soma=soma+numero;
10 |         }
11 |         scanf("%d", &numero);
12 |     }printf("%d", soma);
13 |     i++;
14 | }

```

Fixed on submission: 6

Observation:

A SUGGESTED SOLUTION

FOR PROFESSORS

Apply the bench test (table test) in code samples with and without the error, compare the results – reinforce by asking the students to solve some exercises

FOR STUDENTS

Solve exercises, add code errors, and ask classmate to find them

ANTI-PATTERN GENERAL DATA

ID	TITLE
C_F1	Missing "return"

EXAMPLE:

```

1 int main (){
2     int a;
3     scanf("%d", a);
4     printf("%d", a);
5 }
```


ERROR TYPE:	Syntax	X	Semantics		Style
--------------------	--------	---	-----------	--	-------

CONTENT: - Function

IN WHAT LANGUAGE WAS THE MISTAKE MADE?	X	C			Python
---	---	---	--	--	--------

PROBLEM:

The lack of return may go unnoticed when the value is not needed in the program, as is often the case with return in the main function. However, the functions developed serve to process something and when programmed to return the value, the result is necessary for the continuity of the program, and a lack of return, in this case, will cause the results to fail. For this reason, a typed function must have a return on completion.

CONNECTIONS TO OTHER ANTI-PATTERNS:

- C_F2 – Missing "{" and / or "}" in function
- C_F9 – Incorrect declaration of function parameters
- C_F10 – "return" x "printf"

EVENTS

Note: In the code snippets presented below, only the anti-pattern question of this table was analyzed. If other errors exist, these errors have been handled in other anti-patterns.

EVENT 1

Student Id: 2670	Total of submissions of the exercise:	4
------------------	---------------------------------------	---

The exercise that was being solved:
Exercise 1.1

Error

```

1 int main (){
2     int a;
3     scanf("%d", a);
4     printf("%d", a);
5 }
```

Occurred in submission: 1
Observation:

Fixed Error

```

1 int main (){
2     int a;
3     scanf("%d", &a);
4     printf("%d", a);
5     return 0;
6 }
```

Fixed on submission: 2
Observation:

EVENT 2

Student Id: 2950	Total of submissions of the exercise:	2
------------------	---------------------------------------	---

The exercise that was being solved:
Exercise 1.1

<p style="text-align: center;">Error</p> <pre> 2 int main(){ 3 int n; 4 scanf("%d, &n); 5 printf("%d, n); 6 }</pre> <p>Occurred in submission: 1 Observation:</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Fixed Error</p> <p style="text-align: center;">?</p> <p>Fixed on submission: Observation: The error has not been fixed.</p>
EVENT 3	
<p>Student Id: 5226 Total of submissions of the exercise: 2</p> <p>The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 1.1</p>	
<p style="text-align: center;">Error</p> <pre> 2 int main(void){ 3 int a; 4 scanf("%d,&a); 5 printf("%d\n",a); 6 }</pre> <p>Occurred in submission: 1 Observation:</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Fixed Error</p> <p style="text-align: center;">?</p> <p>Fixed on submission: Observation: The error has not been fixed.</p>
EVENT 4	
<p>Student Id: 5554 Total of submissions of the exercise: 5</p> <p>The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 4.2</p>	
<p style="text-align: center;">Error</p> <pre> 15 int fat (int n) 16 { 17 int ft = 1; int i=1; 18 19 if (n<0){ 20 printf (" -1 \n"); 21 } 22 else { 23 while (i < n) { 24 i = i + 1; 25 ft = ft * i; 26 } 27 28 return (ft); 29 } 30 ... }</pre> <p>Occurred in submission: 3 Observation: The "fat" function does not return any value if the value of "n" received by the parameter is less than "0". The student did not realize that in this case, the function of type "int"</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Fixed Error</p> <p style="text-align: center;">?</p> <p>Fixed on submission: Observation: The error has not been fixed.</p>

is without "return".

**A SUGGESTED SOLUTION
FOR PROFESSORS**

Programming in front of the students, making the error appear – reinforce by asking students to develop new codes

FOR STUDENTS

Study one or more anti-patterns, introduce to classmate and reinforce with exercise

ANTI-PATTERN GENERAL DATA

ID	TITLE			
C_F2	Missing “{“ and / or “}” in function			
EXAMPLE:				
<pre> 1 #include <stdio.h> 2 int main() 3 int n; 4 scanf("%d",&n); 5 printf("%d",n); </pre>				
ERROR TYPE:				
X	Syntax		Semantics	Style
CONTENT: - Function				
IN WHAT LANGUAGE WAS THE MISTAKE MADE?				
X	C			Python
PROBLEM:				
Opening and closing curly braces are mandatory in function declaration; their absence causes a compilation error.				
CONNECTIONS TO OTHER ANTI-PATTERNS:				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - C_F1 – Missing “return” - C_F9 – Incorrect declaration of function parameters - C_F10 – “return” x “printf” 				
EVENTS				
<p>Note: In the code snippets presented below, only the anti-pattern question of this table was analyzed. If other errors exist, these errors have been handled in other anti-patterns.</p>				
EVENT 1				
Student Id: 5730		Total of submissions of the exercise:		2
The exercise that was being solved:				
Exercise 1.1				
Error		Fixed Error		
<pre> 1 #include <stdio.h> 2 int main() 3 int n; 4 scanf("%d",&n); 5 printf("%d",n); </pre>		<pre> 1 #include <stdio.h> 2 int main(){ 3 int n; 4 scanf("%d",&n); 5 printf("%d",n); 6 } </pre>		
Occurred in submission: 1		Fixed on submission: 2		
Observation:		Observation:		
EVENT 2				
Student Id: 3167		Total of submissions of the exercise:		8
The exercise that was being solved:				
Exercise 1.1				

Error	Fixed Error
<pre> 1 #include int main () { 2 int b = a; 3 sacnf("%d", b); 4 printf("%d\n", n); </pre>	<pre> 1 #include int main () { 2 int b = 0; 3 sacanf("%d", b); 4 printf("%d\n", b);} </pre>
<p>Occurred in submission: 1 Observation:</p>	<p>Fixed on submission: 2 Observation: Although many other errors persist, it was in the 2nd submission that the student noticed the lack of the closing brace.</p>

EVENT 3		
Student Id: 2950	Total of submissions of the exercise:	5
The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 3.1		

Error	Fixed Error
<pre> 1 #include <stdio.h> 2 int main(void){ 3 int a, b, c; 4 scanf("%d %d %d", &a, &b, &c); 5 if(a+b+c==180) 6 printf("Sim %d %d %d", a, b,c); 7 else 8 printf("NAO"); </pre>	<pre> 1 #include <stdio.h> 2 int main(void){ 3 int a, b, c, soma; 4 scanf("%d %d %d", &a, &b, &c); 5 soma = a+b+c; 6 if(soma==180) 7 printf("Sim %d %d %d", a, b,c); 8 if(soma!=180) 9 printf("NAO %d", soma); 10 } </pre>
<p>Occurred in submission: 1 Observation:</p>	<p>Fixed on submission: 5 Observation: The student insisted on changing the selection structure from the 2nd to the 4th submission and only in the 5th submission could he compile the code by closing the function. Even the selection structure of the first submission was better designed by using the "else".</p>

EVENT 4		
Student Id: 2243	Total of submissions of the exercise:	2
The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 2.2		

Error	Fixed Error
<pre> 3 int main(void) 4 { 5 int a, b; 6 scanf ("%d%d", &a, &b); 7 if (a<b) printf("1"); 8 else printf("0"); 9 return 0; </pre>	<pre> 3 int main(void) 4 { 5 int a, b; 6 scanf ("%d%d", &a, &b); 7 if (a<b) printf("1"); 8 else printf("0"); 9 return 0; 10 } </pre>
<p>Occurred in submission: 1 Observation:</p>	<p>Fixed on submission: 2 Observation:</p>

FOR PROFESSORS
Explanation using blackboard and projector – reinforce the concept using Kahoot
FOR STUDENTS
Solve exercises, add code errors, and ask classmate to find them

ANTI-PATTERN GENERAL DATA

ID	TITLE
C_F6	Incorrect call of a typed function

EXAMPLE:

```

20 int soma (int a, int b)
21 {
22     return (a+b);
23 }
...
30 int main (void)
31 {
...
33     soma (a, b);
    
```

ERROR TYPE:	Syntax	X	Semantics	Style
CONTENT:	- Function			
IN WHAT LANGUAGE WAS THE MISTAKE MADE?	X	C	Python	

PROBLEM:

When calling a typed function, it is necessary for the caller to be prepared to receive the returned value.

CONNECTIONS TO OTHER ANTI-PATTERNS:

EVENTS

Note: In the code snippets presented below, only the anti-pattern question of this table was analyzed. If other errors exist, these errors have been handled in other anti-patterns.

EVENT 1

Student Id: 1858	Total of submissions of the exercise:	10
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The exercise that was being solved:
Exercise 4.1

Error

Fixed Error

```

20 int soma (int a, int b)
21 {
22     return (a+b);
23 }
24
25 float media (int a, int b)
26 {
27     return (a+b)/2;
28 }
29
30 int main (void)
31 {
32     scanf ("%d %d", &a, &b);
33     soma (a, b);
34     printf ("%d", soma);
35     media (a, b);
36     printf ("%f", media);
37 }

```

Occurred in submission: 1

Observation: Line 33, except the semicolon, should replace "soma" on line 34. The same for lines 35/36. Another option would be to assign the returned value to a variable.

```

20 int soma (int a, int b)
21 {
22     return (a+b);
23 }
24
25 float media (int a, int b)
26 {
27     return (a+b)/2;
28 }
29
30 int main (void)
31 {
32     int a, b, sum, med;
33     scanf ("%d %d", &a, &b);
34     sum = soma (a, b);
35     printf ("%d", sum);
36     med = media (a, b);
37     printf ("%1f", med);
38 }

```

Fixed on submission: 3

Observation: The error was fixed on lines 34 and 36.

EVENT 2

Student Id: 1963

Total of submissions of the exercise:

12

The exercise that was being solved:
Exercise 4.1

Error

```

3 int main (void) {
4     int n1, n2;
5     scanf("%d %d", &n1, &n2);
6     soma(n1, n2);
7     media(n1, n2);
8 }
9
10 int soma (int a, int b) {
11     return a+b;
12 }
13
14 int media (int a, int b) {
15     return (a+b) / 2.0;
16 }

```

Occurred in submission: 1

Observation: Incorrect call on lines 6 and 7.

Fixed Error

```

3 int main (void) {
4     int n1, n2;
5     scanf("%d %d", &n1, &n2);
6     printf("%d", soma(n1, n2));
7     printf("%f", media(n1, n2));
8 }
9
10 int soma (int a, int b) {
11     return a+b;
12 }
13
14 int media (int a, int b) {
15     return (a+b) / 2.0;
16 }

```

Fixed on submission: 2

Observation: In lines 6 and 7, the function call was placed inside "printf", solving the problem.

EVENT 3

Student Id: 5906

Total of submissions of the exercise:

4

The exercise that was being solved:
Exercise 4.1

Error

Fixed Error

```

1 int soma(int a, int b){
2
3     return a+b;
4 }
5
6 float media (int a, int b){
7
8     return (a + b)/2.0;
9 }
10
11
12 int main (void){
13
14     int soma(int a, int b);
15     float media (int a, int b);
16     int a,b;
17     scanf ("%f %f", &a, &b );
18     printf ("%f\n", media);

```

```

12     calc = soma(num1, num2);
13     med = media (num1, num2);

```

Occurred in submission: 1

Observation: Lines 14 and 15 call the "soma" and "media" functions respectively, but incorrectly because the return value is not handled.

Fixed on submission: 3

Observation: The values returned were stored in the variables "calc" and "med".

EVENT 4

Student Id: 1781

Total of submissions of the exercise:

14

The exercise that was being solved:

Exercise 8.1

Error

```

24 | k=determineSeOrdenado(int j,int v[i]);

```

Occurred in submission: 1

Observation: The problem with this call is the declaration of "j" and "v". In function calls, "int" within parentheses cannot exist.

Fixed Error

```

24 | k=determineSeOrdenado(j, v[i]);

```

Fixed on submission: 2

Observation:

A SUGGESTED SOLUTION

FOR PROFESSORS

Apply the bench test (table test) in code samples with and without the error, compare the results – reinforce by asking the students to solve some exercises

FOR STUDENTS

Study one or more anti-patterns, introduce to classmate and reinforce with exercise

ANTI-PATTERN GENERAL DATA

ID	TITLE		
C_F9	Incorrect declaration of function parameters		
EXAMPLE:			
ERROR TYPE:	X	Syntax	Semantics
CONTENT:	- Função: passando parâmetro		
IN WHAT LANGUAGE WAS THE MISTAKE MADE?	X	C	Python
PROBLEM:			
Parameters are variables that will receive values from where the function was called so that it can perform the proposed task. These variables need to be declared in parentheses immediately after the function name at the place of its creation. Each of these variables is given a type, placed immediately before its name and are separated from each other with commas.			
CONNECTIONS TO OTHER ANTI-PATTERNS:			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - C_F1 – Missing “return” - C_F2 – Missing “{“ and / or “}” in function - C_F10 – “return” x “printf” 			
EVENTS			
Note: In the code snippets presented below, only the anti-pattern question of this table was analyzed. If other errors exist, these errors have been handled in other anti-patterns.			
EVENT 1			
Student Id: 1830		Total of submissions of the exercise: 10	
The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 4.1			
<p style="text-align: center;">Error</p> <pre style="font-family: monospace;"> 2 int soma(a, b){ 3 int sum; 4 sum=a+b; 5 return sum; 6 } 7 int media(a, b){ 8 int med; 9 med=(a+b)/2.0; 10 return med; 11 }</pre>	<p style="text-align: center;">Fixed Error</p> <div style="text-align: center; font-size: 2em;">?</div>		
Occurred in submission: 1 Observation: Lines 2 and 7 have parameters “a” and “b” incorrectly declared.	Fixed on submission: Observation: The error has not been fixed.		
EVENT 2			
Student Id: 2040		Total of submissions of the exercise: 4	
The exercise that was being solved:			

Exercise 4.1**Error**

```
3 int soma(a,b)
4 {
5   int s;
6   s = a+b;
7
8   return(s);
9
10 }
```

Occurred in submission: 1**Observation:** Line 3 has parameters "a" and "b" incorrectly declared.**Fixed Error****Fixed on submission:****Observation:** The error has not been fixed.**EVENT 3****Student Id:** 3139**Total of submissions of the exercise:**

7

The exercise that was being solved:
Exercise 4.1**Error**

```
3 float media(a,b){
4   float media = 0;
5   media = (a+b)/2.0;
6   return media;
7 }
```

Occurred in submission: 2**Observation:** Line 3 has parameters "a" and "b" incorrectly declared.**Fixed Error****Fixed on submission:****Observation:** The error has not been fixed.**EVENT 4****Student Id:** 2131**Total of submissions of the exercise:**

4

The exercise that was being solved:
Exercise 4.1**Error**

```
3 int soma(a,b)
4 {
5   int s;
6   s = a + b;
7
8   return s;
9 }
```

Occurred in submission: 2**Observation:** Line 3 has parameters "a" and "b" incorrectly declared.**Fixed Error**

```
3 int soma(int a, int b)
4 {
5   int s;
6   s = a + b;
7
8   return s;
9 }
```

Fixed on submission: 3**Observation:****A SUGGESTED SOLUTION
FOR PROFESSORS**

Programming in front of the students, making the error appear – reinforce by asking students to develop new codes

FOR STUDENTS

Study one or more anti-patterns, introduce to classmate and reinforce with exercise

ANTI-PATTERN GENERAL DATA

ID	TITLE
C_F10	"return" x "printf"

EXAMPLE:

```

2  int main (){
    ...

9  resultadofatorial = fat(n);
10
11
12  return 0;
13  }
14
15  int fat (int n)
16  {
    ...

27  printf ("Resultado: %d \n", ft);
28  return (ft);
29  }
    
```

ERROR TYPE:	Syntax	Semantics	X	Style
--------------------	--------	-----------	---	-------

CONTENT:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data Output Function - Function: Return value
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IN WHAT LANGUAGE WAS THE MISTAKE MADE?	X	C		Python
---	---	---	--	--------

PROBLEM:
 When the function is set to return the calculated value, it must return it, and the responsibility for printing lies with the function that receives the return and not with the function that generated the result.

- CONNECTIONS TO OTHER ANTI-PATTERNS:**
- C_F1 – Missing "return"
 - C_F2 – Missing "{" and / or "}" in function
 - C_F9 – Incorrect declaration of function parameters

EVENTS

Note: In the code snippets presented below, only the anti-pattern question of this table was analyzed. If other errors exist, these errors have been handled in other anti-patterns.

EVENT 1

Student Id: 5226	Total of submissions of the exercise:	5
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The exercise that was being solved:
Exercise 7.2

Error	Fixed Error
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```

20 int potencia(x,n) {
21     while (contador != n){
22         resultado = resultado * x;
23         contador = contador + 1;
24     }
25     printf("%d", resultado);
26     return 0;
27 }

```


Occurred in submission: 1

Observation: The function should return "result" on line 26 and the "printf" call on line 25 should be in the function where it was called.

Fixed on submission:

Observation: The error has not been fixed.

EVENT 2

Student Id: 2950

Total of submissions of the exercise:

3

The exercise that was being solved:
Exercise 2.2

Error

```

2 int main(){
3     int a, b;
4     scanf("%d %d", &a, &b);
5     if(a>=b)
6         return 0;
7     if(a<b)
8         return 1;
9 }

```

Occurred in submission: 1

Observation: The result should be printed and not returned, as was done on lines 6 and 8.

Fixed Error

```

2 int main(){
3     int a, b;
4     scanf("%d %d", &a, &b);
5     if(a>=b)
6         printf("0");
7     if(a<b)
8         printf("1");
9 }

```

Fixed on submission: 2

Observation:

EVENT 3

Student Id: 5098

Total of submissions of the exercise:

5

The exercise that was being solved:
Exercise 2.2

Error

```

9     if (a>b){
10         return 1
11     }
12     else{
13         return 0
14     }

```

Occurred in submission: 1

Observation: The values "1" and "0" should be printed and not returned, as was done on lines 10 and 13.

Fixed Error

```

7     if (a>b){
8         printf("1");
9     }
10    else{
11        printf("0");
12    }

```

Fixed on submission: 4

Observation:

EVENT 4

Student Id: 5554

Total of submissions of the exercise:

5

The exercise that was being solved:
Exercise 4.2

Error

```
1 #include <stdio.h>
2 int main (){
3
4     int n, resultadofatorial;
5
6     printf ("Digite um numero inteiro: ");
7     scanf ("%d", &n);
8
9     resultadofatorial = fat(n);
10
11
12     return 0;
13 }
14
15 int fat (int n)
16 {
17     int ft = 1; int i=1;
18
19     if (n<0){
20         printf (" -1 \n");
21     }
22     else {
23         while (i < n) {
24             i = i + 1;
25             ft = ft * i;
26         }
27         printf ("Resultado: %d \n", ft);
28         return (ft);
29     }
30 }
```

Occurred in submission: 2

Observation: The "fat" function returns the result of the calculation for the "main" function which receives this value in the variable "resultadofatorial" (factorial result) (line 9), but the result is printed inside the "fat" function and not in "main", after receiving the value (line 9).

Fixed Error

```
1 #include <stdio.h>
2 int main (){
3
4     int n, resultadofatorial;
5
6     printf ("Digite um numero inteiro: ");
7     scanf ("%d", &n);
8
9     resultadofatorial = fat(n);
10    printf ("Resultado: %d \n", resultadofatorial);
11
12    return 0;
13 }
14
15 int fat (int n)
16 {
17     int ft = 1; int i=1;
18
19     if (n<0){
20         printf (" -1 \n");
21     }
22     else {
23         while (i < n) {
24             i = i + 1;
25             ft = ft * i;
26         }
27
28         return (ft);
29     }
30 }
```

Fixed on submission: 3

Observation: Error partially corrected on the next submission because "-1" is still being printed on "fat" (line 20) instead of returning this value to be printed on "main" on line 10. If the result was "-1", "Fat" will print "-1" and "main" will print some "garbage" existing in the memory inside the variable "resultadofatorial" (factorial result), usually the value "0".

A SUGGESTED SOLUTION FOR PROFESSORS

Apply the bench test (table test) in code samples with and without the error, compare the results – reinforce by asking the students to solve some exercises

FOR STUDENTS

Study one or more anti-patterns, introduce to classmate and reinforce with exercise